

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: TRIM71.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of TRIM71 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human
11 embryonic stem cell.

12 Citations

- 13 1. Liu, Q., Chen, X., Novak, M.K., Zhang, S. and Hu, W., 2021. Repressing Ago2 mRNA translation
14 by Trim71 maintains pluripotency through inhibiting let-7 microRNAs. *elife*, 10, p.e66288.
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16 Trim71 cooperates with microRNAs to repress Cdkn1a expression and promote embryonic stem cell
17 proliferation. *Nature communications*, 3(1), p.923.
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